

The Influence of Work Life Balance and Employee Engagement on Performance with Job Characteristics as a Moderating Variable in MSMEs in Gianyar Regency

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Abstract: The aim of this research is to explain the role of job characteristics in moderating the influence of work life balance and employee engagement. This research was conducted on MSMEs in the weaving craft industry in Gianyar district with a sample of 140 respondents through purposive sampling. Collection techniques use interviews and questionnaires. Data were analyzed using Moderating Regression Analysis. The research results show that work life balance has a positive and significant effect on the performance of MSME employees, employee engagement has a negative and significant effect on the performance of MSME employees, job characteristics moderate the influence of work life balance on the performance of MSME employees, and job characteristics moderate the influence of employee engagement on the performance of MSME employees. The implication of this research is that it can contribute ideas to MSME actors. The contribution of thought in question is that MSMEs continue to develop the results of this research in a practical way that can become a reference for other researchers who want to research work life balance, employee engagement, job characteristics and performance. Theoretically, this research also provides an understanding that work life balance, employee engagement, job characteristics and performance can actually provide benefits or value to businesses so that they can improve the performance of MSMEs.

Keywords: work life balance, employee engagement, job characteristics, performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Human Resources (HR) is an important aspect in determining the development of a company (Nugrahani & Priyono, 2022). Every company that is founded definitely has the hope that in the future it will experience rapid development in the business scope of its organization and hopes to be able to create high performance in its business field. From the results of the pre-survey results of the pre-survey results of the craftsmen in the MSME weaving craft industry in Gianyar Regency, the majority of their marital status is married. Employees who are married and have a family are often faced with difficult choices in their dual roles, both carrying out their duties at home and carrying out their duties as employees. Employees must be ready to work on weekends, holidays or certain holidays if they receive orders that must be completed immediately. Employees also admit that working hours often change and having to work at the same time as holidays or holidays is a problem. Another thing that is felt is that employees have less time with their families and related matters outside of work. The balance between work and personal life is an important factor and every company needs to consider it when creating policies to maintain work efficiency. A good work life balance will provide a positive atmosphere, so that employees can feel satisfaction at work, and will have a positive influence on the company's progress. Employees who

have high performance for a company is not an easy thing because it requires many factors that employees need to contribute to the organization. One of them is employee engagement as the degree of willingness to unite oneself with work, invest time, ability and energy in work and consider work as the main part of one's life. Positive feelings and high enthusiasm for work can be called employee engagement (Sucahyowati & Hendrawan, 2020). An indication of a lack of sense of work involvement in the MSME weaving industry in Gianyar district is a lack of attachment to their place of work where there is a tendency to only work to carry out obligations without paying attention to the relationships that are built between employees and the company in an effort to achieve the company's goals optimally. Work carried out with the pattern of coming, completing the work assigned, then just going home has a bad impact on the company's performance (Sucahyowati & Hendrawan, 2020). Well-designed jobs will be able to attract and retain employees and provide motivation to produce quality work. Job characteristics also determine a person's suitability for a particular field of work which influences a person to be more successful in the field he is working in, with concentration accompanied by responsibility. Quality human resources can be achieved if the job characteristics received by human resources are in accordance with the capacities possessed by employees. Efforts to provide job characteristics that are in accordance with human resource capacity are activities that must be carried out by every company so that employee abilities and job satisfaction increase as determined by the company (Rahmadalena & Asmanita, 2020).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Performance

A person's performance is an individual thing, because each person has a different level of ability in carrying out their duties (Robbins & Judge, 2016). Increasing individual employee performance will improve agency performance, so employee performance is an important concept for agencies to achieve their goals (Nugrahani & Priyono, 2022). The conclusion that can be drawn from these definitions is that employee performance is the result of work that has been achieved in terms of quality and quantity in carrying out their duties and responsibilities in accordance with predetermined standards.

Work life balance

Work life balance is a broad concept that involves setting appropriate priorities between "work" (career and ambition) on the one hand and "life" (happiness, free time and family) (An Naafi', 2022). Work life balance is a aspect of an individual's ability to find a rhythm that can balance responsibilities at work with responsibilities outside of work, which can provide opportunities to be able to carry out and prioritize both by trying to minimize mutual interference between the two (Atthohiri & Wijayati, 2021). Based on several opinions regarding work life balance above, it can be concluded that work life balance is a person's ability to balance their responsibilities for work and things that are not related to work.

Employee Engagement

An Naafi' (2022) stated that employee engagement is the main factor that plays a role in productivity, performance and company survival. Employee engagement in a company is an important element as the most effective "business driver" to support the company's success. With the attachment between employees and the company, it will create a harmonious relationship between employees and the company so that they will give maximum effort in carrying out their work.

Job Characteristics

Job characteristics are defined as the nature of tasks which include the amount of responsibility and various tasks carried out by employees (Rahmadalena & Asmanita, 2020). Job characteristics are the nature of an employee's duties which include types of tasks, responsibilities, and the level of satisfaction obtained from the characteristics of the job itself (Muhammad, 2017). Furthermore, according to Robbins & Judge (2016) job characteristics are an approach to designing jobs that shows how jobs are described into five core dimensions, namely diversity of skills, task identity, task meaning, autonomy and feedback.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The population of this study were SMEs in the weaving craft industry in Gianyar Regency. The sampling technique used in this study was non-probability sampling with a purposive sampling method, in which the sample was determined with certain considerations or criteria. The sample criteria in this study are as follows: Minimum education level is high school

or equivalent, respondents who have worked for more than 5 years and are domiciled in Gianyar Regency, 140 respondents who meet the criteria in this study. The analytical tools in this study are validity and reliability tests. Then the data analysis technique is Regression Moderating Analysis (RMA)

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results of this research will be studied further through interaction testing techniques (Moderated Regression Analysis), which is a special application of linear multiple regression. This research also tests the role of job characteristics in moderating the influence of work life balance and employee engagement on the performance of MSME craftsmen in Gianyar Regency. In this research, the influence of work life balance and employee engagement on the performance of MSME craftsmen in Gianyar Regency was calculated using the SPSS 21.0 for Windows program in table 4.1.

Table 4.1 Results of Moderated Regression Analysis

$Y = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_1M + \varepsilon \dots\dots\dots(1)$						
$Y = 4.313 + 0,162X + 0,209X_2 + 0,270 M + 0,241 X_1M + 0.009 X_2M$						
SE =	0,051	0,035	0,033	0,100	0,097	0,054
T =	84,474	4,621	6,245	2,706	2,487	0,175
Sig =	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,008	0,014	0,861
$R^2 = 0,484$ $F = 22,292$ $Sig = 0,000$						

The Moderated Regression Analysis equation can be interpreted as follows:

$X_1 = 0.162$ indicates that work life balance has a positive effect on performance, if work life balance increases then performance will increase by 0.162

$X_2 = 0.209$ indicates that employee engagement has a positive effect on performance, if employee engagement increases then performance will increase by 0.162

$M = 0.270$ indicates that job characteristics have a positive effect on the performance of MSME craftsmen in Gianyar Regency, if job characteristics increase then performance will increase by 0.270

$X_{M1} = 0.241$ Work life balance interaction with work characteristics has a coefficient of 0.241 meaning that with the work characteristics, the positive effect of work life balance on strengthened performance.

$X_{M2} = 0.009$ Employee engagement interaction with work characteristics has a coefficient of 0.009 meaning that with the work characteristics, the positive effect of work life balance and employee engagement on strengthened performance.

Determination Analysis

Determination analysis was carried out to determine the extent of variation in the independent variables, namely work life balance (X_1) and employee engagement (X_2), job characteristics (M) on the performance variable (Y). based on the SPSS results which can be seen in table 4.2

Table 4.2 Determination Analysis

Model R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.695 ^a	0.484	0.462

Based on Table 4.2, it can be seen that the r square value = 0.484. The analysis uses the following formula:

$$D = x \times 100\%$$

$$D = 0.484 \times 100$$

$$D = 48.4\%$$

Based on these results, it is known that the R2 value = 48.4%, which means that 48.4% of the performance of MSME craftsmen in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency is influenced by the variables work life balance and employee engagement, and job characteristics, and the remaining 51.6 percent influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

Model Feasibility Testing (F Test)

Based on the results of the F Sig value analysis. of 0.000, it can be said that H1 is accepted because the F Sig value. 0.000 < 0.05. The conclusion is that work life balance and employee engagement and job characteristics simultaneously have a significant effect on the performance of MSME craftsmen in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency. The model used in this research is feasible and can be used for analysis.

Hypothesis test

1) The Effect of Work Life Balance on Performance

Work life balance has a Beta value of 0.816 and a Sig value. is 0.020, then it can be said that H1 is accepted because the Sig value. 0.020 < 0.05. The conclusion is that work life balance has a positive and significant effect on performance, in other words, as work life balance increases, the performance of MSME craftsmen in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency will increase. So the first hypothesis is accepted.

2) The influence of employee engagement on performance

Employee engagement has a Beta value of 1.413 and a Sig value. is 0.001, then it can be said that H2 is accepted because the Sig value. 0.001 < 0.05. The conclusion is that employee engagement has a positive and significant effect on performance, in other words, as employee engagement increases, the performance of MSME craftsmen in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency will increase. So the second hypothesis is accepted.

3) The influence of job characteristics on performance

Job characteristics have a Beta value of 0.207 and a Sig value. is 0.001, then it can be said that H2 is accepted because the Sig value. 0.001 < 0.05. The conclusion is that job characteristics have a positive and significant effect on performance, in other words, as job characteristics improve, the performance of MSME craftsmen in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency will increase. So the third hypothesis is accepted.

4) Work Life Balance on Performance with Job Characteristics as a Moderating Variable

work life balance interaction has a Beta value of 0.241 and a Sig value. is 0.004, then it can be said that H4 is accepted because the Sig value. 0.004 < 0.05. The conclusion is that job characteristics moderate the influence of work life balance on the performance of MSME craftsmen in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency. Where the resulting moderating effect is to strengthen the relationship, in other words if there are job characteristic variables then the influence of work life balance on the performance of MSME craftsmen in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency will be further strengthened, so that the fourth hypothesis is accepted.

5) The influence of employee engagement on performance with job characteristics as a moderating variable

Employee engagement interaction has a Beta value of 0.009 and a Sig value. is 0.861, then it can be said that H4 is accepted because the Sig. 0.042 < 0.05. The conclusion is that job characteristics moderate the influence of employee engagement on the performance of MSME craftsmen in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency. Where the resulting moderating effect is to strengthen the relationship, in other words if there are job characteristic variables then the influence of employee engagement on the performance of MSME craftsmen in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency will be further strengthened, so that the fifth hypothesis is accepted

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion, several conclusions can be drawn, namely:

- 1) Work life balance has a positive and significant effect on the performance of MSMEs in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency.
- 2) Employer engagement has a positive and significant influence on the performance of MSMEs in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency,

- 3) Employee engagement has a positive and significant influence on the performance of MSMEs in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency,
- 4) Job characteristics moderate the influence of work life balance on the performance of MSME employees in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency.
- 5) Job characteristics moderate the influence of employee engagement on the performance of MSME employees in the weaving industry in Gianyar Regency.

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